

kg N/ha as urea, 18 kg P/ha as single superphosphate, and 25 kg K/ha as muriate of potash, and was irrigated to 6 cm 19 times. Rainfall was 502 mm.

At salinity level of 4 dS/m, only BPT11563 showed a 50% yield reduction (see table). At 6 dS/m, CSR6, CSRS, RP4-14, and CSR2 had

yield reductions ranging from 31.6 to 39.1%; BPT3402, MTU8089, CSR 1, Phalguna, MTU2400, WGL44752, BPT3301, BPT11503, and MTU2077 had moderate yield reductions ranging from 40.3 to 49.6%; other varieties showed more than 50% yield reduction. □

Effect of saline irrigation water on yield at Bapatla, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			Reduction (%) at 6 dS/m
	1 dS/m	4 dS/m	6 dS/m	
Phalguna	5.9	4.9	3.4	43.5
RP4-14	3.5	2.5	2.1	38.9
MTU2077	6.2	4.9	3.1	49.6
MTU2400	4.2	3.2	2.3	45.0
MTU6637	3.1	2.1	1.4	53.3
MTU8089	5.4	3.9	3.2	41.2
BPT3291	3.6	2.5	1.7	52.7
BPT3301	4.3	2.9	2.2	48.6
BPT3402	5.6	4.4	3.4	40.3
BPT5899	5.4	3.3	2.1	61.5
BPT8233	4.3	3.7	2.0	52.5
BPT8250	3.4	1.9	1.5	55.3
BPT8424	3.5	2.8	1.6	52.9
BPT9921	4.7	3.5	2.3	52.1
BPT9938	3.4	2.1	1.6	51.6
BPT9942	5.4	3.4	2.6	52.2
BPT11503	4.9	3.3	2.5	49.2
BPT11563	4.5	2.2	1.8	59.4
BPT11660	5.0	4.1	2.4	52.9
CSR1	3.3	2.2	2.0	41.2
CSR2	3.6	2.5	2.2	39.1
CSR5	3.3	2.5	2.1	37.3
CSR6	5.1	4.4	3.5	31.6
WGL44644	3.0	2.1	1.4	55.1
WGL44752	3.4	2.8	1.9	45.1
WGL44753	3.7	2.7	1.7	54.3
WGL44759	3.7	2.3	1.6	56.3

CD for varieties = 0.21

CD for EC levels = 0.07

CD for EC levels × varieties = 0.36

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DEEP WATER

A promising rice culture for shallow waterlogged conditions

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We evaluated medium-duration rice cultures suitable for shallow waterlogged conditions (50 cm) in artificially inundated fields 1984-85 and 1985-86. Water depth was maintained at 50 cm from vegetative stage to maturity.

Of eight entries, IET5656 (Sona/RPW6-13) withstood

submergence best (see table). IET5656 has 146 d duration and medium height (125 cm), and is nonlodging. Grain is medium bold with white rice.

Yields of rice cultures under waterlogging. Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85 and 1985-86.

Culture	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
IET5656	4.2	146
Co 42	3.8	147
CR 1009	3.6	155
Ponni	3.5	141
White Ponni	3.4	140
Pankaj	3.5	144
NLR9672	3.2	150
TNR1 (local check)	2.7	153

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Seedling tolerance for dehydrating wind

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We evaluated the reaction of 105 varieties to an unusual heavy, dehydrating wind during Jun-Oct 1986.

The 105 varieties from different sources were sown 2 rows each in

Rice varieties or cultures showing resistance to wind. Tamil Nadu, India.

Score	Varieties or cultures
1	10% of population with leaf tops dry
	ASD1, ASD7, ASD8, ASD9, TPS1, IR28178-45-4, AS25839, CR1030, DPI831, NaagSamba, Arivikiruvai, Karuthavellai, Manjal Saradi, Thattaravellai, Vellarakkan, and TNAU80030
3	25% of population with leaf tops dry
	Co 33, Co 41, IR64, TKM9, AD9246, AD85001, AS688, PL 29, ADT35, ASD5, ASD11, ASD15, IR44, IR46, IR52, IR54, IR62, Ponni, AS28883, CR1014, IET6711, IR2193-26-3-5-2, TM4506, TP1974, Kochisamba, Kattisamba, Panamarasamba, Samba, Tanjore Samba, Yanaisamba, Muntakka, KutrichaRasali, Saradi, Ponraiyan, Kallanthattaravellai, Thulanadan, Valsaraimundan, GEB24, Co 19, and PTB15
5	40% of population with leaf tops dry
	ASD16, ADT30, ADT31, ADT33, ADT36, IET1444, IET4786, IR36, IR58, IR60, Arupatham Kuruvai, AD7486, TM8089, IR20, IR34, IR48, Paiyur-1, W. Ponni, Bhavani, AD9408, AS2887, AS24976, BR10, BS19, C22, CR1009, IET5233, IET7301, IET7590, Channavellai, Co 40, BCPI, BPT1235, and TNAU89994
7	50% of population with leaf tops dry
	IR50, PY3, Thiriveni, Co 42, Co 43, Co 44, IR5, IR8, IR42, AD14185-1, AS781/1, AS6860/1, AS6860/2, AS23972 and AS24711